

THE EFFECTS OF THE FIBRE BRIDGING ON THE ENTIRE STRAIN FIELD OF FATIGUE CRACKS IN FIBRE METAL LAMINATES

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SUMMARY

This paper presents both experimental and analytical investigations on the effects of bridging fibres on the entire strain field of fatigue cracks in Fibre Metal Laminates. Digital image correlation provided visualization of both the entire strain fields and delamination shape, which have been compared with those analytically calculated.

Keywords: Fibre metal laminates, bridging fibres, digital image correlation, fatigue crack growth

INTRODUCTION

Fibre Metal Laminates (FMLs) have been developed in the past to improve the fatigue performances of laminated aluminium structures by adding fibres in the bond line. FMLs exhibit failure mechanisms of both metals and composites. The metallic layers show fatigue crack growth similar to monolithic metals, crack initiation and propagation, while the composite layers, which are insensitive to the fatigue loading, show delamination at the metal-composite interfaces. The fibres transfer load over the fatigue crack in the metal layers and restrain the crack opening. This phenomenon is called fibre bridging. These complex mechanisms of crack growth in the metal layers and delamination growth at the interface between metal and fibre layers, if in optimal balance, result in the excellent fatigue characteristics for which FMLs are known.

The fatigue crack growth behaviour of FMLs has been investigated extensively during the last two decades for constant and variable amplitude loading sequences [1-4]. In the last decade several analytical prediction methods have been developed to describe the crack growth behaviour in FMLs under constant amplitude loading [5-10].

The bridging fibres, acting as a second load path in the wake of the crack, carry part of the load, reducing the stress intensity at the metal crack tip; consequently, the full field deformation of the metal layers, including the plastic zone ahead the crack tip, reduces. This paper presents both experimental and analytical investigations on the effect of bridging fibres on the deformation field in FMLs. Digital image correlation (DIC) was employed to measure the deformation field of the external metal layer of different FMLs, considering both saw-cut and fatigue crack configurations. The experimental

measurements have been compared with the deformation fields obtained by means of analytical modelling [9,11] considering linear-elastic solutions [12,13]. This paper provides an insight into the “fibre bridging” phenomenon in FMLs, pointing out the limitations of the analytical linear-elastic solutions employed to calculate the deformation field when high static loads are applied.

FATIGUE CRACKS IN FMLs

In this section the crack bridging effect characterizing a fatigue crack in FMLs is briefly described when two load conditions are applied: fatigue loading and quasi-static loading.

Figure 1 Crack bridging in FMLs [14].

Fatigue crack propagation in the FML consists of crack growth in the metal layers and delamination at the metal/prepreg interfaces in the wake of the crack. The intact fibre layers in the wake of the crack act as a second load path over the crack, reducing significantly the load transferred around the crack tip in the metal layers (Figure 1). As a result of the fibre bridging, the crack growth rates in the metal layers are significantly lower compared to the crack growth rate in an equivalent monolithic metal under the same applied load conditions. Due to the balance between crack propagation and delamination growth, the observed crack growth rates are approximately constant over a significant period of the crack growth life [9].

The analytical calculation of the fibre bridging [7,9] showed a dependency of the bridging stress from the delamination shape and a quasi-constant value of the bridging stress along the wake of the growing crack, except in the vicinity of the crack tip where a stress peak is present, see Figure 2. This stress distribution has been experimentally observed measuring the strain of the fibre/prepreg layer bonded on the outside of a panel (inverted lay-up laminate) using digital image correlation (DIC) [15].

The behaviour of FMLs containing a fatigue crack under static load is influenced by the bridging fibres in the same manner as in the fatigue load case. The failure sequence under quasi-static load is characterized by a stable crack growth followed by instability leading to a fast crack growth until final failure. In case of high static load, the large amount of plasticity (plastic zone) which develops in the metal layers is restrained by the bridging fibres. Increasing the applied load increases the bridging stress, see Figure

2, and the shear stress at the metal/fibre interface along the delamination front. When this shear stress reaches the critical value, the fatigue delamination starts growing in the loading direction [16,17]. Delamination growth is beneficial in order to let the fibres strain more along a large delamination length, thus reducing the stress and avoiding premature fibre failure.

Figure 2 Fibre stress measured with DIC on the external prepreg along three fatigue cracks ($\sigma=110\text{MPa}, R=0.05$) and under quasi-static load ($\sigma=140\text{MPa}$ and 160MPa) in a 2024-T3 /S2-glass inverted laminate, and comparison with analytical calculations [15].

EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

In the following sections the experiments are described with respect to materials and test procedure. Details on DIC and on the image analysis of are provided in [15,18,19].

Materials

Several tests have been performed on CCT specimen made by two different types of FMLs, using 2024-T3 as metal constituent and S2-glass/FM94 or M30-carbon/DT120 as fibre/prepreg constituent. The panels were manufactured with dimensions of 140 by 290 mm. Two panels of Glare 3-3/2-0.4 were manufactured containing a 20mm long saw-cut and a 20mm long fatigue crack respectively. The fatigue crack was obtained by applying cyclic load under constant amplitude, starting from a 5mm notch. For this two panels static loads were applied, as described in the next section, while for panels made of Glare 3-2/1-0.4 and Glare-carbon 3-2/1-0.3 only fatigue loading were applied.

Test executions

The entire strain fields of both fatigue crack and saw-cut configurations were measured using digital image correlation (DIC) [15,18,19] employing a digital camera system with an electronically controlled x-y-z table. For the Glare 3-3/2-0.4 panels, images

were taken at different static loads and, after the DIC was performed, visualizations of the strain fields for both fatigue crack and saw-cut configurations have been obtained for each load level. Figure 3 illustrates the test execution procedure for both saw-cut and fatigue crack configurations.

Figure 3 Schematic illustration of the test execution for both saw-cut and fatigue crack configurations.

For the other two panels, Glare 3-2/1-0.4 and Glare-carbon 3-2/1-0.3, the images were captured under the maximum fatigue applied load.

ANALYTICAL APPROACH

The crack bridging model developed by Alderliesten [9] was employed to calculate the two-dimensional displacement, stress, and strain fields in the FML metal layers. The model solves for the distribution of crack bridging stress along the delamination by solving the compatibility relation between the metal layers and the bridging fibre layers along the delamination boundary, where the vertical displacements of the cracked layers and the bridging layers must be equal. Since each of these displacements are in part functions of the unknown bridging stress distribution, numerical methods allow the bridging stress to be found.

The left side of Eqn. 1, below, gives the crack opening of the cracked metal layer, which Alderliesten [9] assumes is nearly equivalent to the displacement at the delamination boundary. Here, superposition is employed to separate that due to the far-field stress, v_{∞} , and that due to bridging, v_{br} . The right side of Eqn. 1 gives the displacement of the reinforcing fibre layers at the delamination boundary. The term, δ_f , represents the displacement due to the elongation of the fibres, and δ_{pp} accounts for shear deformation in the prepreg layer at the delamination boundary. All of the terms in Eqn. 1 are functions of x since the bridging stress, crack opening, and fibre elongation may vary along the boundary, and compatibility must hold at all x .

$$v_{\infty}(x) - v_{br}(x) = \delta_f(x) + \delta_{pp}(x) \quad (1)$$

Eqn. 1 is solved numerically by discretizing the bridging load along the delamination boundary (Figure 4), writing the total v_{br} as a sum of the displacement at a bar element due to each of the bridging loads at all bar elements:

$$v_{br}(x) = \sum_i v(x, x_i) w_i \quad (2)$$

Figure 4 Schematic illustration of the crack length discretization [11].

Alderliesten's method [9] originally relied on the assumption that the difference between the crack opening displacement and the displacement of the metal layers at the delamination boundary was negligible. Because the entire displacement field is of interest, the method was modified to calculate the exact displacement of the cracked metal layers along the delamination boundary. Therefore, the relations used by Alderliesten for v_{∞} and v_{br} for the opening displacement of the crack flanks were replaced by formulations for the displacement at the height of the delamination.

Using Westergaard stress functions, Z_I and \bar{Z}_I , from [12,13] augmented with the correction for uniaxial loading given by [20], the displacement due to far-field stresses at any position, (x,y) , can be written:

$$v_{\infty}(x, y) = \frac{1}{2G} \left(\frac{\kappa+1}{2} \text{Im} \bar{Z}_I - y \text{Re} Z_I - \frac{\kappa-3}{2} \frac{\sigma_{\infty}}{2} y \right) \quad (3)$$

The displacement, measured at point (x,y) , due to the bridging load j at any given point, (x_j, y_j) , along the delamination boundary is given by the following equations, adapted from [12]:

$$v_{br,j}(x, y, x_j, y_j) = \frac{1 - \frac{\nu}{1+\nu}}{G} \text{Im} \bar{Z}_I - \frac{y}{2G} \text{Re} Z_I \quad (4)$$

The total displacement due to bridging stress at a given point is calculated similarly to Eqn. 2:

$$v_{br}(x, y) = \sum_j v_{br,j}(x, y, x_j, y_j)w_j \quad (5)$$

A consequence of revising the crack bridging model to use expressions for the exact displacement of the metal layers at the delamination heights was that the displacement at any arbitrary point could be calculated with the same expressions:

$$v(x, y) = v_{\infty}(x, y) - v_{br}(x, y) \quad (6)$$

A complete explanation of each term of the presented equations and discussion of incorporating the exact displacements in the Alderliesten's method is given in [11].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The strain fields data obtained in the experiments contain information on plasticity in the metal layer and the shape of fatigue delamination. The experimental results are presented and discussed for a selection of load cases and material lay-ups.

In an FML with a saw-cut, the strain field shape and size is determined by the mutual interaction between metal and fibre layers. The orthotropic contribution of the fibre layers induces a re-distribution of the stress/strain such that the 'wing-angle' and size of the plastic zone are affected by the stiffness of the fibre/prepreg system [19].

If a fatigue crack configuration is considered, the bridging fibres in the wake of the crack introduce a larger orthotropic contribution inducing a further variation of the deformation field. In Figure 5 a comparison between the strain fields of a saw-cut and a fatigue crack, under the same applied load, is provided. The images refer to two panels of Glare 3-3/2-0.4 with a 20 mm saw-cut and 20 mm fatigue crack ($2a_0=5\text{mm}$), respectively.

Figure 5 Comparison of the strain field ahead of a 20 mm saw-cut (a) and a 20 mm fatigue crack (b) in Glare 3-3/2-0.4 under an applied stress of 200 MPa (Scale in %)

The applied load was increased quasi-statically, as qualitatively illustrated in Figure 3, and images were captured for each load level. Figure 5 shows two examples referring to an applied load of 200 MPa, where the colours refer to different strain levels in y-direction. The images cover a relatively small area in vicinity of the crack tip, including

the last 5mm of the crack length. Figure 6 illustrates the full sequence of the plastic zone development due to the increasing load, comparing both saw-cut and fatigue crack. The plastic zone is defined as the part of the strain field where $\epsilon_{yy} = \epsilon_{0.2}$, where $\epsilon_{0.2}$ represent the yield stress of the metal .

Figure 6 Comparison of the plastic zone between a 20 mm saw-cut and a 20 mm fatigue crack in Glare 3-3/2-0.4 under quasi-statically increased loads, measured using DIC

Figure 7 Qualitatively illustration of the stress distribution around the crack tip of a saw-cut and fatigue crack configurations, and visualization of the plastic zone extension above and below the delamination boundary (right).

The bridging fibres induce both a reduction of the size and a variation of the shape of the plastic zone. The extension of the plastic zone in x-direction is constrained by the bridging fibres and the two wings of the plastic zone develop mainly in vertical

direction, except for the wing tips that are bent downward. If the load is further increased, the plastic zone spreads above and below the delaminated area, as shown in the right hand side of Figure 7 (black arrows).

This phenomenon cannot occur in a saw-cut configuration because there is no mechanism which attracts load in the wake of the crack, as schematically illustrated in Figure 7. Under certain geometrical condition, further increments of the load could lead to a situation where the entire area surrounding the crack yields.

As known, the fatigue crack growth in FMLs is dominated by the bridging fibres which reduce the stress intensity at the crack tip, see Eqn. 7,

$$K_{tip_{FML}} = K_{\infty} - K_{br} \quad (7)$$

where K_{∞} and K_{br} denote the stress intensity factor of the metal layer due to the far-field load and the stress intensity factor due to the bridging fibres respectively. In monolithic metal and metal laminate, K_{tip} depends on the crack length and increases with the corresponding fatigue crack extension. As reported in [21], in an FML the plastic zone size and shape in front of a fatigue crack maintain constant with the crack growth due to the increasing number of bridging fibres. This behaviour is shown in Figure 8, where the 0.2% strain contour is considered. The size and shape maintain about constant for large part of the crack growth until the edge effect takes place, increasing the stress intensity.

Figure 8 Propagation of the delamination and development of the 0.2% strain contours under fatigue loading, $\sigma_{max}=150$ MPa and $R=0.05$, for a 2024-T3/carbon 3-2/1-0.4, measured using DIC

Following the approach proposed in [11], displacement and strain fields have been analytically calculated for a selection of FML. With equation 3 and 5, the displacements of the metal layers due to bridging and the far-field stresses, calculated using classical laminate theory for the applied loads and thermal residual stresses, were calculated and superimposed to get the displacement over a grid of points. In order to compare the

results to the DIC measurements, in which the images of the specimens captured under load are compared with those taken with no applied load, a second bridging and displacement calculation was made with no applied load, but with residual stresses, and the displacement results were subtracted from those calculated with an applied load.

In Figure 9 a comparison between analytical calculations and experimental measurements is illustrated for Glare 3-2/1-0.3. The predicted delamination shape and the strain contour for two strain levels are compared with the results from DIC. In general, the trends along each line agree with the DIC results in the vicinity of the crack tip, however the exact values are not quite the same. The agreement seems to be better for relative high strain value (0.3%), while for smaller strain values (0.15%) the difference between predicted and measured strain contour increases. This can be explained with the very small values of strain that have to be measured with DIC, which are largely influenced by the error of the measurement [18,19]. In addition, the analytical formulation is based on the compatibility of the displacements along the wake of the crack, thus excluding any influence of the area in front of the crack. As reported in [19], the strain field in front of the crack tip in an FML is influenced by the orthotropic contribution provided by the fibre layers, which is related with the stiffness and orientation of the fibres. It is plausible that the discrepancies between predictions and measurements could be reduced including the effect of the of the fibre layers along the uncracked section.

Figure 9 Glare 3-2/1-0.3, $a = 11.7$ mm, $\sigma = 100$ MPa, comparison between experimental measured and predicted delamination and strain contours

Being based on a purely linear-elastic approach, the analytical description proposed in [11] shows predictive limitations in case small-scale yielding is violated, e.g. high static load is applied. For FMLs small scale yielding occurs even if a relative high load is applied. Figure 10 compares experimental measurements with analytical calculations for

a panel made of Glare 3-3/2-0.4, statically loaded at 200 MPa. Also in this case the model predicts quite well the 0.5% strain contour (area in the vicinity of the crack tip), while the contour at 0.25% strain is much over predicted. Despite the relative high load applied to the panel, the plastic zone size maintains in the order of the crack length (small-scale yielding) enabling a linear-elastic solution of the problem.

Figure 10 Glare 3-3/2-0.4, $a = 10\text{mm}$, $\sigma = 200\text{ MPa}$, comparison between experimental measured and predicted delamination and strain contours

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of bridging fibres in the wake of a fatigue crack in FMLs has been investigated from the point of view of the deformation field and plastic zone.

It has been experimentally investigated how the bridging fibres influence the development of the strain field with respect to a configuration without bridging fibres. The plastic zone reduces in size and in shape. An increment of the applied load induces the plastic zone to spread above the delamination boundary.

An FML with a growing fatigue crack shows an almost constant size of the strain field and plastic zone. This is due to the almost constant value of the stress intensity factor which characterizes a large part of the crack growth process.

The analytical calculations showed good predictive capability, enabling the calculation of the entire strain field, accounting for the bridging effect. A good agreement has been observed in the vicinity of the crack tip, while strain contours with lower strain value are not predicted well by the model.

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